

ACTIVE METHODOLOGIES IN BIOLOGY TEACHING: A BIBLIOGRAPHIC REVIEW

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5635392

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ABSTRACT: This work presents a literature review that aimed to investigate the use of active methodologies in the discipline of Biology, based on an analysis of the literature available in scientific articles in indexed journals database. The specific studies found for PBL in Biology teaching represent at most 1.8% of published works. The results point to few studies on active methodologies in Biology teaching and show the relevance of implementing it.

Keywords: Active methodologies, PBL, Biology teaching, Literature, Science teaching.

1. INTRODUCTION

There has always been a lot of discussion around teacher training. Understanding how to teach how to be a teacher is not an easy task, and there is no cake recipe for it. Carvalho & Gil-Pérez (2011) state that a teacher's activity goes far beyond the act of giving classes, and training is not a simple sum of scientific preparation and general education courses, as previously thought. For Krasilchick (1987), the teacher needs freedom of action regarding the way of teaching and needs encouragement to change their behavior in the classroom.

Teaching has been the focus of numerous researches, and it is common in these, when approaching teaching practice, to raise negative issues related to the teaching profession. Several problems are listed, the most commonly mentioned are related to the work environment, lack of structure and material, devaluation of teachers, lack of student interest and lack of support from society in general (SILVA, 2019).

As for the teaching of science, in addition to the problems of teaching in general already mentioned, other obstacles to the teaching-learning process are observed. Among the most discussed in the literature are: poor preparation of teachers, the syllabus of curriculum guides, poor quality of textbooks, lack of laboratories, lack of material for practical classes, obstacles created by the school administration and work overload (ANDRADE and MASSABNI, 2011).

Complaints that previously referred only to deficiencies in the methodological area have expanded to encompass the training of professionals in relation to knowledge of the subjects themselves, leading to insecurity in relation to the class, low quality of classes and strict dependence on textbooks (KRASILCHIK, 1987). Another aggravating factor is that the science teacher has been, according to history, exposed to a series of challenges, including having to

keep up with scientific and technological discoveries, firmly managed and implemented in everyday life, and make scientific advances and theories compatible with elementary school students, making them available in an accessible way (LIMA, VASCONCELOS, 2006).

ACTIVE METHODOLOGIES IN BIOLOGY TEACHING

Taking a didactic posture that makes sense for the student recommends the use of a wide variety of languages and resources. It is necessary to work the contents so that they have their starting point in the daily lives of students and teachers, which will allow the student to decide and choose better as a citizen. Contents that flow to ensure students understand the fundamental concepts of biology.

In this search, several methodologies have been proposed and studied over time. The so-called traditionalist teaching is confused with the formal education institution itself. Although, according to Leão (1999), the traditional school has undergone countless transformations throughout its existence, it resists time.

he theories of education that guided the traditional school are confused with the very roots of the school as we conceive it as an educational institution” and that the traditional school continues to exist in a similar way to what it was in its beginnings (LEÃO, 1999).

Mizukami (1986) describes traditionalist teaching as an approach that is not implicitly and explicitly based on empirically validated theories, but on educational practice. It is a form of teaching centered on the teacher and in it the adult is considered a finished, ready man. The student, on the other hand, is considered a miniature adult who needs to be updated, and the teacher's role is to transmit knowledge. Furthermore, in this approach, the school would be the only place where learning takes place and it can be acquired and accumulated.

The traditional approach to teaching is based on the assumption that intelligence is a faculty that makes man capable of storing information, from the simplest to the most complex. From this perspective, it is necessary to decompose the reality to be studied in order to simplify the knowledge heritage to be transmitted to the student who, in turn, should only store the results of the process (LEÃO, 1999).

Several researches in the teaching field have studied the feasibility of this type of teaching and questioned its adequacy to the teaching standards required by the present time. Other teaching methodologies or approaches emerge as a way of opposing traditional, humanist, socio-cultural, behavioral, cognitive/constructivist teaching. The latter being more evident in more recent studies.

Initially proposed by Jean Piaget, according to Mizukami (1986), the educational process plays an important role in causing the student's cognitive and mental imbalance in order to be able to progressively build notions and operations. It is important to respect each stage of the students' development and recognize learning as being more than a product of the environment, people or facts that are external to the student. Knowledge, according to this approach, is considered a continuous construction and the teacher-student relationship is one of cooperation for the teaching-learning process.

Leão (1999) emphasizes that constructivism is neither a method nor a technique, this new teaching paradigm is a posture towards the acquisition of knowledge. Becker (1993) states that in this conception nothing is ready, knowledge is not given, in any instance, as something finished. It is an “individual's interaction with the physical and social environment, with human symbolism, as a world of social relations” (BECKER, 1993. p.88).

Inspired by these new constructivist/cognitivist teaching paradigms, the so-called active methodologies emerged. Andrade and Campos (2005) report that the active methodology is a teaching-learning process in which the student is placed as the protagonist and the teacher assumes a supporting role. Thus, the student's autonomy is encouraged so that he is able to build his own knowledge. For Andrade and Massabni (2011), the teacher remains responsible for directing the student, but always allowing them to make discoveries that contribute to their education. In this way, the moments of study extend far beyond the class schedule, in an integrative and stimulating way for the student.

Among the types of active methodologies are: “project-based learning”, where students build their knowledge in a collaborative way, through the solution of challenges; “problem-based learning”, based on case solving and interdisciplinarity. Another type of methodology is “gamification”, which uses games and challenges in classroom situations; the “inverted classroom”, a technique that mixes the digital and classroom experience. Finally, there is “peer learning”, based on the collective and collaborative work of pairs; and “storytelling”, which in turn, narrative creation techniques (COLLOR, 2019).

In this type of teaching, the student is placed as the protagonist of their learning and the teacher assumes the role of instructor of the path to be followed, giving students the tools for them to develop cognitively. In addition, active teaching cares for the formation of citizens in addition to academic training, thinking about the relationships of students with the world in which they live (BORGES et al 2014).

Among the most studied active methodologies are Problem-based Learning (PBL); Teaching by Research (EI); and Demonstration of Interactive Lessons (ILD). These didactic-pedagogical methodologies are centered on the student and, in the last 30 years, they have been applied in schools and there are numerous studies that test their efficiency in the field of psychopedagogy. What varies between these methodologies is how they are applied, but they all aim at a common goal, which is to make the student use their previous knowledge and seek to develop these and learn new ones through practical and interactive activities (BORGES et al 2013; FELICETTI et al 2012; BARREIRO, 1992). Given these assumptions,

Considering that problem-based learning addressed in Biology themes in Basic Education, especially in High School, is a topic little discussed in academic and scientific circles, this work is justified by a bibliographic review. In addition, the work may contribute to filling this gap in the literature regarding the approach to this topic.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This literature review was carried out with the aim of understanding the use of active methodologies in the discipline of Biology, from a detailed analysis of the literature available in scientific articles and in indexed journals database. For that, the advantages of applying active methodologies against traditional methodologies were pointed out, seeking the results of works with the application of PBL in Biology; as well as pointing out the efficiency of the implementation of the PBL methodology in the discipline of Biology in high school, according to the publications.

Bibliographic research is conceptualized by Pizzani et al (2012) as a literature review on the main theories that guide scientific work, this research is called bibliographic survey or bibliographic review. In other words, it is a search for a particular subject in books, periodicals, newspaper articles, Internet sites or other sources.

Bibliographic research is carried out based on the available record, resulting from previous research, in printed documents, such as books, articles, theses, etc. It uses data or theoretical categories already worked on by other researchers and duly registered. The texts become sources for the themes to be researched. The researcher works from the contributions of the authors of the analytical studies contained in the texts (SEVERINO 2002).

The search took place in the context of active methodologies in Biology teaching, through articles, dissertations and theses published between the year 2000 and the first half of 2020. The searches were carried out on online research platforms : Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), Journal Portal of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) and the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD).

The descriptors used to consult the online databases were made in ascending order of the terms “active methodologies”; “active methodologies in teaching”; “active methodologies in Biology teaching”; “PBL”. A survey of the quantities of work carried out within each spectrum was carried out, characterizing the research as quantitative, but also with a breakdown of the work of the last descriptor, analyzing them in a qualitative way.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the collected sample, it was observed that the works that have as a basic object of study, the use of active methodologies is quite vast, with different types of studies. However, when it comes to works with specific studies on the teaching of Biology, it is still little studied, with few results in the researched bases.

In the SciELO database, it is possible to see that the works that address the topic are recent, so that most researches were carried out in the last decade. The keywords “PBL”; “Active methodologies”; and “Active methodologies in teaching” were the ones that returned the most results. However, "Active methodologies in science education" and "Active methodologies in Biology teaching" together resulted in only 12 results, as shown in table 1. As shown in table 1, the result for "Active methodologies in biology education", specifically brought a result (0.15% of the total) and no title. This percentage portrays the small volume of research on the subject, when compared to other descriptors.

Table 1 – Number of productions on the SciELO Periodical Portal

SCIELO					
Keyword	Total	Title	2020-2010	2009-	Older
PBL	250	36	193	57	1992
PBL in teaching	75	0	57	18	2003
Active methodologies	185	43	168	17	1999
Active methodologies in teaching	133	07	120	13	1999
"Active methodologies in teaching"	5	1	5	0	2010
Active methodologies in science teaching	11	two	11	0	2010
Active Methodologies in Biology Teaching	01	0	1	0	2018

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2020

The CAPES Journal Portal was the base that returned the most results for the searched keywords. According to table 2, “PBL” led to 25,682 results, but the keywords “Active methodologies in science teaching” and “Active methodologies in Biology teaching” brought 26 results. The result for “Biology”, in particular, represents 0.01%, as shown in table 2 and no title. The works are recent, but found in 1974, which may lead to the understanding that the research and use of PBL in teaching has been part of the universe of educators since the 70s, a time without the presence of technologies, internet and other tools present in today's daily life.

Table 2 - Number of productions on the CAPES Periodical Portal

CAPES PERIODIC					
Keyword	Total	Title	2020-2010	2009-	Older
PBL	25,682	4,621	16,665	9,017	1974
PBL teaching	281	24	221	60	1995
PBL science teaching	8	0	5	3	2008
Active methodologies	855	119	743	112	1994
Active methodologies in teaching	481	61	440	41	1999
Active methodologies in science teaching	22	1	22	0	2010
Active Methodologies in Biology Teaching	4	0	4	0	2012

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2020

The BDTD Portal also brings important and broader results than the previous databases in relation to the studied topic. The results of the surveys "Active methodologies" and Active methodologies in teaching" were the highest, with 478 and 420 in total for each keyword, respectively, as shown in table 3. "Active methodologies in science teaching" revealed seven titles and a total of 280 results. With regard specifically to the teaching of Biology, two titles and 32 citations in total were returned, which represents 1.8% of all keywords used, as can be seen in table 3. It is also observed that the works are quite recent, so that the oldest found refers to the year 2002. The terms are more comprehensive and with a number of similar results for each descriptor.

Table 3 - Number of productions on the BDTD Periodicals Portal

BDTD							
Keyword	Total	Title	2020-2010	2009-	Older	dissertations	Theses
PBL	243	21	198	45	2002	179	64
PBL teaching	217	11	178	39	2002	162	55
PBL science teaching	157	two	134	23	2002	121	36
Active methodologies	478	98	462	16	2004	380	98
Active methodologies in teaching	420	60	410	10	2004	333	87
Active methodologies in science teaching	280	7	273	7	2004	226	54
Active Methodologies in Biology Teaching	32	two	29	3	2004	25	7

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2020

Barros, Santos and Lima (2017) report that the idea of an innovative pedagogical practice is a starting point for the unknown, often representing a threat to the position conquered. Only through a reflective, critical and committed practice can autonomy, freedom, dialogue and the confrontation of resistance and conflicts be promoted. They also realized through the studies that “the perspectives of active methodologies are predominant in relation to the experiences applied in disciplines or teaching and care activities. Such experiences are motivated by personal and institutional interests, engaging teachers in the application of pedagogical innovations”.

Frantz, Marques, Nunes and Marques (2018) related the use of active methodologies with digital technologies. They applied activities that involved hybrid teaching with the use of the technological resource Moodle in teaching physics. Through the study, the authors noted that "the experience lived through practice with hybrid teaching provided a process of building knowledge in a network, by enabling the diversity of tools for its construction".

Silva, et al (2015) discuss the use of PBL and active methodologies in health education and propose the use of a new active methodology, the problem discussion cycle (CDP). They explain the methodology that is inspired by PBL but contains 12 steps. The conclusions they reached were that “The use of innovative pedagogical approaches has been imperative in view of the need to train professionals able to meet the demands of a world in permanent transformation process”.

Cacho, et al (2016) report on the experience of the active methodology “Objective Structured Clinical Examination” (Object Structured Clinical Examination – Osce). The subjects of this research were 29 students from the seventh period of the Physiotherapy course. The authors' conclusions were that "the Osce methodology applied to the assessment of "knowing how to do" in physical therapy practice at the three levels of health care has satisfactory to excellent inter-examiner reliability, and can be a useful method for the evaluation process of professional training in health ”.

Gomes, et al (2010) analyzed fifty questionnaires that correspond to 100% of the researched universe, filled out at the end of the course by students of the Public Policy on Mental Health discipline in the first semester of 2007. According to the authors, “it was possible to provide it to the student of graduation course from the Health Sciences Centers (CCS) and Philosophy and Human Sciences (CFCH) learning and experiences in the field of Public Health Policies, specifically in the area of mental health, through the use of pedagogical strategies that value teaching centered on the student and their ability to build knowledge with autonomy”.

Segura and Kalhil (2015) presented the characteristics and steps for the application of three strategies based on the Active Methodology. The application of these strategies in Science Teaching aims to promote integrated learning in the context of citizens ready to face the challenges of everyday life. Each step has its importance, but within the cognitive learning process, the attitudinal dimension makes the student able to develop the necessary skills to become competent in the area of interest. Finally, the investigation of these strategies in science teaching, within the classroom, becomes important for the production of scientific knowledge and for the strengthening of scientific culture in Education.

According to MARÍN, et al (2017), in the problem-based learning methodology, project-oriented learning or school research, it is identified that resources play a fundamental role, especially in vivo natural resources that correspond to living beings and ecosystems of the territory, as well as the context in which these resources are inserted and the different resources that help students to collect and record information in field classes. The experiences present paths to be explored in the teaching of biodiversity in the Brazilian context, thus opening the doors for further research on the subject.

According to Guerra and Teixeira (2016), the results found show that when active methodologies were implemented, the grades of students in the Accounting course had historically been falling year after year. From the adoption of active teaching methodologies, we realized that, even without the increase in grades, they have been gaining maturity over the period, perhaps due to the evolution or maturity of teachers, students or those responsible for training so that active activities were passed on in the rooms. It was found that, although the grade of those who failed students dropped with the classes given with the active methodology, the average difference in grades between those who passed and those who failed also dropped.

Silva and Souza (2019) report the need to work on the environmental theme in a contextualized way so that the student can understand the relevance of the study on environmental issues regardless of the training course that has been their choice, knowing that the environment will always influence people's lives, directly or indirectly. The discussion of the accidents that occurred made it possible to clarify doubts about the contents taught in the theoretical classes and, based on the students' questions, interdisciplinary questions on the studied topic were addressed, as well as the exchange of experiences and knowledge among the groups of students. .

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The productions found in the scientific literature point out that implementing this methodology is a possibility to integrate the use of various technological resources to the pedagogical practice. It is noticed that the studies regarding the specific application in the teaching of Biology are still incipient and researches about the potential of this methodology for teaching the aforementioned discipline are relevant.

The implementation of PBL in Biology teaching can be seen as a tool with high potential for improvement in the teaching-learning process, leading the student to effectively participate in the process as a protagonist and agent for constructing knowledge, as well as making the teacher a subject learning mediator, which makes the student learn, valuing the experiences and experiences. Such implementation can be carried out in different ways, such as the use of formal teaching materials, videos, games, practices and communication and information technologies.

Knowing the importance of active methodologies, their benefits, the possibility of successfully implementing the teaching-learning process, PBL should be more applied by educators working in Biology teaching (ANDRADE and CAMPOS, 2005). In addition to the application, it is up to educators and researchers themselves to develop other works in this sense, in order to enrich the literature, even knowing that it is already developing contemporary works, to seek new instruments that enhance PBL and even make new discoveries.

Knowing that this work does not intend to exhaust the subject and given the incipience of specific studies on the application of active methodologies for the teaching of Biology, further research is needed that seeks to review the literature, know such application and its tools according to the proper specificities of the theme, in addition to the proper practical application to compare the potential benefits of using these instruments.

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